

Model of Optimization of DMOs' Marketing Communication via Internet

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Abstract

The main goal of this paper is to propose a model of optimization of DMOs' marketing communication via internet. In this context, special attention is paid on measuring and optimizing communication strategies of DMO-s and linking the effects of campaigns carried out by the DMO with business results of tourism products providers. The proposed model of optimization contributes to the important task of DMOs: justifying to stakeholders the spent of budget by proving return on investment in marketing communications with the market regardless of their involvement in sales. The model takes into account the classic premise of cooperation between DMOs and tourism providers, all with the goal of fostering economic exchanges of tourism products on the market.

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1. Introduction

Destination management organizations (DMOs) are faced with a transition from their traditional role of organizations primary involved in promotion into organizations involved in sales and management of destinations. In practice it is evident that there is a problem in measuring the influence of DMO marketing activities on sales results achieved by destination tourism providers in case no affiliate marketing program is set. A model that overcomes this issue is presented in this paper.

This paper is composed of five parts. After the introduction, part two reviews relevant findings of previous researches regarding measuring advertising and marketing communication performance on sales. A model of optimization of DMOs marketing communication via internet and a research investigating its requisite is presented in part three. Part four is dedicated to the discussion, while conclusion is given in the fifth part.

2. Theoretical review

Evaluation techniques of destination marketing activities can be roughly divided into two main categories: tracking and conversion studies and the second - quasi-experiments and econometric modeling where all these methods usually rely on some manifestation of established survey methods to generate data (Smith, 2009). Tracking studies attempt to establish the effects of a promotional campaign by monitoring potential visitors' awareness, perceptions, intentions and travel patterns and involve pre and post campaign monitoring (Smith, 2009). Econometric and experiential methods can be combined to further prove causality of campaigns as they isolate its influence, usually by including control groups. The focus in this paper will be on conversion studies which investigate actual conversion, unlike tracking studies which focus on assessing if a visit is more likely to occur.

The use of conversion studies was pioneered by Woodside and Reid in 1974 (Cai, 1998). The main objective of conversion studies is to determine the percentage of potential customers who inquired about a tourism destination that have later on visited. They estimate gross and net proportion of inquirers: gross conversion rate involves the inquirers that took a trip to the destination after requesting travel information, while the net conversion rate involves

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the inquirers who traveled to the destination as a direct result of the travel information they received (Kaplanidou & Vogt, 2003).

Inquiry conversion is the most common marketing assessment tool in travel industry (Turco & Dry, 1993). Woodside and Dubelar (2003) claim that conversion study are the main method used by DMOs to assess their promotional efforts, as also established by a HSMAI study in 2002.

Criticisms against conversion study include the incompleteness of information gathered since some conversions occur without additional enquiry and the uncertainty of what is being measured: if the original advertising or the information sent after the enquiry. They also do not take into account if interest for the destination existed before the campaign and thus tend to over-estimated advertising campaign significance (Johnson and Messmer, 1991; McWilliams and Crompton, 1997). Another issue is the problem of non-response, as they are based on surveying those who requested additional information. That way they reflect the attitudes of respondents willing to participate in the survey. Surveys are usually undertaken from two to six months after the end of the campaign (Pratt et al., 2009) excluding visits that might have occurred after. Subjective answers on which are based for gathering information affect the credibility of results.

Although the monitoring of DMO indirect conversion is a known phenomenon, it is largely unexplored in domestic and foreign literature, and, according to author' research conducted, poorly applied in practice. Horan, McCarty and Frew (2002) have a narrow definition of indirect bookings or indirect sales conversion - „all bookings which at some point have touched the visitscotland.com website whether they were online, or ultimately came via letter, phone, fax, email“. They used website data log analysis of VisitScotland and surveyed general managers of accommodation facilities to calculate the indirect conversion of the DMO website. Specifically, the general managers provided data on sales that were achieved from visitors who on their websites came thanks to a link on the website of DMO (i.e. the web analytic tools of hoteliers VisitScotland.com was a source of traffic conversion). Three researches studying the indirect conversion visitscotland.com have been conducted so far (Frew, Horan and McCarty 2001, McCarty and Frew 2002, Horan and Frew 2009) focusing on the same combination of data – web analytics and surveys.

As Smith (2009) concludes, there is a great potential to improve the process of measurement of DMOs promotion; by working out on elimination of disadvantages of current methods, it possible to provide a „simple method that can be used regularly and cost-effectively by destinations“. Taking this into account there is a need to propose a model of optimization DMO marketing communications via internet.

3. Model of optimization of DMOs' marketing communication via internet

In order to determine whether there is a need for proposing a model for DMO marketing communication optimization in practice, a field research was conducted. An electronic questionnaire was distributed in 2010 to a sample of 19 DMO at regional level, including all coastal Croatian DMOs or Tourist Boards (seven in total) and DMOs from Lisbon and Madeira (Portugal), Catalonia and the Balearic Islands (Spain), Provence-Alpes-Cote d'Azur and Languedoc-Roussillon (France), Tuscany and Friuli Venezia Giulia (Italy), Peloponnese and Attica (Greece), Istanbul and Antalya (Turkey). The results regarding monitoring indirect conversion showed that only one DMO (7,14%) tracks sales of destination tourism product by tourism providers (e.g. hotel) generated by customers that had previously visited DMOs websites. Operationally, this feedback of generated sales that a DMO can take credit for is carried out using promotional codes visitors insert themselves in online booking systems of accommodation providers. None of them is able to connect this situation to a step earlier: know which marketing campaign led to the DMO website, then to the hotel website and finally resulted in a sale. Respondents where ask to rate the importance of the implementation of such a model in terms of marketing communication strategy optimization. The average score is 4,29 on a scale of 1 (min.) out of 5 (max.) based on 7 answers (Slivar Tiganj, 2012) which confirmed the need for implementation of such a model presented in Figure 1.

The proposed model starts with the creation of a marketing strategy results from company's objectives, and is preceded by the situation analysis (steps one and two). In the third step marketing strategy is formed, followed by the formation of the marketing plan (fourth step). A special emphasis is given to shaping the marketing

communication plan which includes both online and offline techniques and tools (fifth step). The sixth step - set up and improvement of monitoring of effects of marketing communication - refers to:

- establishing the monitoring of marketing communication internally within the DMO system (at local level, regional and national), which is especially important in the case when one of the DMO does not sell tourism products and refers to other DMOs that do.

- establishing a system for monitoring the effects of DMO communication externally with tourism providers.

The seventh step is the implementation of marketing communication, in accordance with the predetermined communication plan. The eighth step is divided into two parts, DMO consumer touchpoints and tourism provider consumer touchpoints. Consumer touch points apply to all modes of interaction with the (potential) customers through: websites, phone, fax, e-mail, through social networks, etc. In terms of consumer touchpoints a special place belongs to websites, bearing in mind the increasingly important role of internet in planning and decision making process about holidaying. DMO's marketing campaigns commonly include links to their own websites, not those of tourism providers (Slivar Tiganj, 2012). However, DMO's marketing communication sometimes may release contact information of tourism providers (e.g. brochures), hence user can also contact tourism providers directly. Through DMO consumer touchpoints, a potential buyer can accomplish a specific action that a DMO counts as a conversion e.g. brochure download (step 9a.). Since DMOs even when selling tourism products themselves do not cease to promote tourism providers, it is possible that a potential customer through one of consumer touchpoints of a DMO, gets the contact of a tourism provider. Seen from the standpoint of sales conversion, the potential customer may buy a particular tourism product from DMOs (if involved in sales) or the same product can be purchased directly from tourism providers to whom DMOs point to (step 9b.). In the first case, it is about direct sales conversion, in the second, indirect sales conversion of DMOs, no matter if achieved online or offline. In a broader sense the term direct sales conversion of DMO may be applied to sales generated internally within the system of DMOs of multiple levels. The tenth step refers to monitoring the performance of overall marketing communication strategy, where it is important to define the parameters to monitor. Clearly, conversion tracking, previously highlighted, is an essential part of this step. Based on the performance of marketing communication it is possible to optimize it (step 11.).

In the process of optimization certainly the hardest role belongs to DMOs at national levels (NTOs –National Tourism Organizations) that sell tourism products. They should strike to find a balance among their own sales, other lower DMOs' sales and sales of tourism providers and coordinate the whole process. To encourage DMOs that sell tourism products to pay equal attention to indirect and direct sales, it is possible to determine an equal commission for both sales.

In order that the described model is feasible within the system of websites of DMOs, it is necessary to set the outbound links from each websites (for monitoring indirect online conversion) and other contact data set to be monitored (for monitoring indirect offline conversion).

DMO websites are official sources of information and should therefore continue to be entry points for relevant travel information of destinations they represent. What is specific to destination marketing is that DMOs with their communication activities act as promoters of tourism products providers. Therefore the integration of joint planning, implementation and monitoring of the effects of that communication is crucial.

Figure 1. Model of optimization of DMOs' marketing communication

Source: authors' work according to D. Chaffey, R. Mayer, K. Johnston et al.: «Internet marketing – Strategy, Implementation and Practice», third edition, Prentice Hall - Financial Times, Harlow, 2006., pp. 137

4. Discussion

The presented model focuses on indirect conversion (sale or other action) achieved by tourism providers as a result of marketing communication of DMOs. It includes all DMO websites and those of tourism providers, therefore the proposed model implies cross-channel optimization of websites. Given that the model takes into account offline and online communication channels, it also contributes to integrated marketing communication of DMO. It is advisable to apply a multi-source attribution system in order to split conversion among DMOs and providers marketing efforts. The implementation of the model involves the cooperation and coordination of tourism providers and DMOs and connects their marketing monitoring methods into a system at the destination level. By connecting DMOs at macro, meso and micro level it is possible to better coordinate their actions within these organization's system.

Lack of model presented in this paper is that it focuses on measuring sales conversions, as a concrete result of specific DMO marketing campaigns. However, without combining it to other methods it is not possible to determine other factors that could also affect the decision of holidaying e.g. whether visitors read online reviews or consulted other sources. Furthermore, the presented model does not take into account the long-term effects of a campaign. It is therefore recommended to combine it with other methods of research such as advertising awareness. When it comes to upgrading the presented model, it is desirable to simplify the ability to track indirect offline conversions compared to what is possible today.

Questions about whether there is even a perfect method of measuring efficiency and return on investment in marketing communications of DMOs - remain unanswered. In any case, it is better to measure anyhow and be aware of the disadvantages of the chosen method and be able to compare results from year to year, than not measure the effectiveness of marketing communication at all. Besides finding the perfect methodology for measuring effectiveness of marketing activities of the DMO, it imposes the need of standardization so the same results could be compared regionally, nationally and internationally.

5. Conclusion

This paper has pointed out the need to manage the process of marketing communication conducted by DMOs in order to improve sales of destination tourism products. The proposed model quantifies the impact of DMOs marketing activities to tourism providers and enables a better optimization of collective marketing communication at the destination level in order to improve not only business results of DMOs (if selling tourism products) but also those of tourism providers. This has somewhat filled the gap in terms of DMO contribution to destination stakeholders, which is especially important in case of those DMOs that are not involved in sales and, in addition to that, are on public funding. This way they are actually given the opportunity to at least partially prove return on investment in marketing communication.

The model presented in this paper overcomes the important issues of subjectivity, non-response and timing of the research as it is not based on collection of user data. It might represent a more adequate solution (simple, cheap and easily accessible) for assessing a bigger picture of promotional effectiveness monitoring. It however does not pretend to prove causality of campaigns and related sales, as this requires additional research and user collected data.

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